

THEORETICAL CONCEPTS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS: CLASSIFICATION AND USAGE

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Annotation: The article covers important information about the theoretical concepts about the classification and the usage of English phraseological units. On the other hand, historical background of phraseological units were noted.

Key words: *transformational grammar, socio-economic, self-contained, ready-made units, collocational dictionaries, psycholinguistics, main preoccupations, adverbial unit.*

In today's process of globalization, the effect of the radical reform of the education system of Uzbekistan is evident in all areas related to this area. The state pays special attention to the teaching and further development of foreign languages in the education system, which is a key sector of socio-economic, political and cultural life of the country, one of the vital factors that directly affect the morale of the population. at the policy level. At a video conference chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on May 6, 2021 on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages, the problems in the system were analyzed in detail and priorities were identified. On this basis, the issue of attitudes to foreign language teaching is addressed in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 No PP-5117 "On measures to bring the promotion of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level": "... education in foreign languages It is no coincidence that the need to develop as a policy priority, radically improve the quality of education in this area,

Vol. 2. Issue 1.

attract qualified teachers to the field and increase the population's interest in learning foreign languages "[1]. This article also provides valuable information about the origin of phraseological units in English, which are considered very important for English language learners, and the main types and uses of them today. So, first, let's dwell on the general characteristic of phraseological units and its history.

Phraseology (from Greek φράσις phrasis, "way of speaking" and -λογία -logia, "study of") is a scholarly approach to language which developed in the twentieth century. It took its start when Charles Bally's notion of locutions phraseologiques entered Russian lexicology and lexicography in the 1930s and 1940s and was subsequently developed in the former Soviet Union and other Eastern European countries. From the late 1960s on it established itself in (East) German linguistics but was also sporadically approached in English linguistics. The earliest English adaptations of phraseology are by Weinreich (1969) within the approach of transformational grammar, Arnold (1973), and Lipka (1992 [1974]). In Great Britain as well as other Western European countries, phraseology has steadily been developed over the last twenty years. The activities of the European Society of Phraseology (EUROPHRAS) and the European Association for Lexicography (EURALEX) with their regular conventions and publications attest to the prolific European interest in phraseology. European scholarship in phraseology is more active than in North America. Bibliographies of recent studies on English and general phraseology are included in Welte (1990) and specially collected in Cowie & Howarth (1996) whose bibliography is reproduced and continued on the internet and provides a rich source of the most recent publications in the field[2].

The consideration of the origin of phraseological units contributes to a better understanding of phraseological meaning. According to their origin all phraseological units may be divided into two big groups: native and borrowed.

Phraseology is a comparatively young field of linguistics which has only relatively recently become established as a self-contained linguistic discipline. Phraseology is pervasive in all language fields. Phraseology is studying phraseological units (set expressions, phraseologisms, or idioms (in foreign linguistics)). Phraseological units differ from free word-groups semantically and structurally:

1) they convey a single concept and their meaning is idiomatic, i.e. it is not a mere total of the meanings of their components

2) they are characterized by structural invariability (no word can be substituted for any component of a phraseological unit without destroying its sense (to have a bee in one's bonnet (not cap or hat).

3) they are not created in speech but used as ready-made units. Unlike a word, a phraseological unit can be divided into separately structured elements and transformed syntactically.

However the subject of phraseology has been a matter of growing interest since the 1930's in applied linguistics amongst different fields as in lexicography with the first collocational dictionaries like the Palmer and Hornby studies for a Dictionary of English as a foreign language, the question about phraseology as special linguistic discipline had not been arisen before the mid-1960s. It is due to the expansive research of soviet school of linguists that phraseology has been established as a discipline in its own right. As one of the most outstanding modern lexicographers, the author of the famous and most reliable Oxford Dictionary of Current Idiomatic English Anthony P. Cowie, pointing out to the indisputable progress of the soviet school of phraseological analysis and its influence on the world linguistics, underlines: "Recognition of phraseology as an academic discipline within linguistics – the term itself, like the adjective 'phraseological', reflects Eastern European usage – is evident not only from vigorous and widespread research activity, but also from the publication of several specialized

Vol. 2. Issue 1.

dictionaries reflecting one theoretical perspective or another... 'Classical' Russian theory, with its later extensions and modifications, is probably the most pervasive influence at work in current phraseological studies and is unrivalled in its application to the design and compilation of dictionaries." .

Nowadays phraseology plays a central role in a wide range of linguistic disciplines such as lexicography, contrastive linguistics, psycholinguistics, foreign language learning and teaching and natural language processing. As phraseology has strong links with several other fields of linguistics restrictions and institutionalization of word combinations or multi-word units should be included in the field of phraseology. Compounds and grammatical collocations are cases in point. This difficulty in establishing what exactly falls under field of phraseology is compounded by the fact that phraseology is a dynamic phenomenon, and displays both synchronic and diachronic variations[3].

Although there is still some considerable discrepancy between linguists as regards the terminology and typology of word combinations and the limits of phraseology itself, there is general agreement that phraseology constitutes a continuum along which word combinations are situated, with the most opaque and fixed ones at one end and the most transparent and variable ones at the other. One of the main preoccupations of linguists working within this tradition has been to find linguistic criteria to distinguish one type of phraseological unit from another (e.g. collocations vs. idioms or full idioms vs. semi-idioms) and especially to distinguish the most variable and transparent multi-word units from free combinations, which only have syntactic and semantic restrictions and are therefore considered as falling outside the realm of phraseology.

According to the type of motivation, three types of phraseological units are suggested: phraseological fusions, phraseological unities and phraseological combinations. Phraseological fusions (e.g. tit for tat) represent as their name suggests the highest stage of blending together. The meaning of components is

Vol. 2. Issue 1.

completely absorbed by the meaning of the whole, by its expressiveness and emotional properties. Phraseological fusions are specific for every language and do not lend themselves to literal translation into other languages. Phraseological unities are much more numerous. They are clearly motivated. The emotional quality is based upon the image created by the whole as in to stick (to stand) to one's guns, i.e. 'refuse to change one's statements or opinions in the face of opposition', implying courage and integrity. The example reveals another characteristic of the type, namely the possibility of synonymic substitution, which can be only very limited. Some of these are easily translated and even international, e.g. to know the way the wind is blowing.

The third group in this classification, the phraseological combinations, are not only motivated but contain one component used in its direct meaning while the other is used figuratively: meet the demand, meet the necessity, meet the requirements. The mobility of this type is much greater, the substitutions are not necessarily synonymical. Now we pass on to a formal and functional classification based on the fact that a phraseological unit functioning in speech may be similar to definite classes of words (nouns, verbs, adjectives, etc.), whereas they also may vary structurally[4].

According to this principle, they distinguish set expressions that are nominal phrases: the root of the trouble; verbal phrases: put one's best foot forward; adjectival phrases: as good as gold; red as a cherry; adverbial phrases: from head to foot; prepositional phrases: in the course of; conjunctive phrases: as long as, on the other hand; interjectional phrases: Well, I never! A stereotyped sentence also introduced into speech as a ready-made formula may be illustrated by Never say die! 'never give up hope', take your time 'do not hurry'.

The above classification takes into consideration not only the type of component parts but also the functioning of the whole, thus, tooth and nail is not a nominal but an adverbial unit, because it serves to modify a verb (e.g. fight tooth

and nail); the identically structured lord and master is a nominal phrase. Moreover, not every nominal phrase is used in all syntactic functions possible for nouns. Thus, a bed of roses or a bed of nails and forlorn hope are used only predicatively.

To sum up all given facts above, it should be noted that the study of any foreign language is impossible without referring to phraseology, which represents one of the most difficult for learning language levels. Idioms — units of speech communication, therefore their study should be carried out with the help of communicative exercises, the content of which is the students' performance of speech acts in terms of real communication or similar to them. It is now commonly accepted that the people who want to master the English language must have knowledge about wide range of complex lexical in English as a foreign language learner. Obviously, in order to command a foreign language deeply, a learner should learn pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary. But the main of them is phraseological units. The English language is full of phraseological units. Obviously, idioms, phrases, phrasal verbs and set expressions, aphorisms, maxims, proverbs and sayings are the main units of any language, without them our language may seem shallow or boring. The ability to use phrasal expressions is a great sign of language.

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